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**FEATURES OF FRUIT, RIPENING AND GROWING OF ARCHI SEEDS IN ARID
MOUNTAIN ZONES OF UZBEKISTAN**

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Annotation: *The article presents the results of a study on the Features of fruiting, ripening and germination of juniper seeds. The time of flowering, ripening of pine berries was determined, the summary data on the quality of pine berries and seeds of forest-forming juniper species, the time of biological dormancy, how to avoid biological dormancy and obtain the results of sowing in a short time were studied. The development of seedlings in natural conditions, the difference between juniper seedlings of various species from each other has been studied.*

Key words: *juniper turkestanica, juniper semiglobosa, juniper seravschanica, seed;seeds, seedlings, pine berries, vegetation, slopes and expositions*

Introduction. Juniper forests, light forests and dwarf thickets (juniper forests) are widespread in the mountainous regions of Central Asia, Crimea, Altai-Sayan mountainous region, the Caucasus and the Far East. [1].

They lose their ecological purpose and diverse protective role, at the same time, they themselves experience the negative impact of such natural processes as soil erosion, mudflows, landslides and avalanches. Due to the decrease in forest cover in the mountains, cases of avalanches, landslides and mudflows have recently become more frequent, causing colossal damage to the national economy and often causing death. The most destructive factor for juniper forests and open woodlands is the anthropogenic factor: unauthorized, mainly forced-selective, logging, unregulated grazing, excessive recreational load, unorganized tourism, brushwood harvesting and forest fires, which cause significant damage to juniper forests. This led to a decrease in forested areas and an increase in low-density plantations and open spaces, digression, and sometimes complete destruction of the soil cover, herbaceous and shrub vegetation in juniper forests and the development of erosion processes. [1].

Scientific literature on scientific and experimental topics is analysed. Used materials on expeditions, reports on afforestation, documents on the basis of juniper.

forests in forestry are collected. The data of meteorological stations, natural conditions at experimental stations are studied. The yield of herbage was determined by the method of mowing on sites of 1 m². To determine the general assessment of the state of juniper stands under the influence of the conservation and grazing regime, the methods developed by the Institute of Forest and Walnut Growing of the Kyrgyz HAH, as well as the Department of Ecology and Forest Protection of the Moscow State University of Forestry (Mozolevskaya, Kataev, Sokolova, 1984) were used. All trees were subdivided into 6 categories, their condition was established by external signs: Category 1- trees without signs of weakening; Category 2 - weakened; Category 3 - strongly weakened, Category 4 - drying out; Category 5 - dead wood of the current year; Category 6 - dead wood of past years [2].

Research results and discussion Juniper are evergreen dioecious, less often monoecious, medium-sized trees or small shrubs. Flowers are collected in small oval-shaped dioecious spikelets. Male (anther) ones are larger, they are laid at the ends of suitable shoots in the previous year before pollination, in June, and after 2-3 months they become quite mature and consist of several pairs of stamens, which look like scales of scutes on which legs. The scutes are located crosswise on the spikelet shaft and bear 4 oval-oblong anther sacs on the upper side. In this state, the spikelets overwinter. During flowering, a drop of sticky liquid emerges from the inlet (pollen inlet), which catches the pollen and draws it into the ovule. Juniper blooms depending on location and weather conditions: in March, April or May [3]. After pollination, the scales of a female spikelet, becoming fleshy, quickly grow into a berry-like formation. Therefore, the fruits of juniper were named - pineapple [3].

Ripening of cones takes two years (sometimes three). But by the end of the first year, they reach the size of a two-year-old and take their characteristic form, however, they have significant differences. Biennial cones berries with ripe brownish dark green resinous flesh. In juniper *turkestanica*, they are black, shiny, in *J. semiglobosa*, they are blue-black, with a thick bluish bloom, and in *J. seravschanica*, they are dark-burgundy, almost black. The seeds in such cones are shiny, brown, hard, quite easily separated from the resinous pulp of the fruit when it is crushed. The cones of the first year of development are green, the pulp is less resinous, light green, the seeds in them are dull, not so hard, it is difficult to separate them from the pulp of the fruit. The described differences between pine berries of the first and last years of development are clearly visible already in August, especially in detached trees and on illuminated parts of the crown in plantations. In connection with the annual setting and two-year ripening of each year, the same tree contains cones of different ages and qualities: the first year immature ones with seeds that do not yet have a developed embryo, and the second year ones - with normally developed seeds and embryos.

Juniper seeds are distinguished by an interesting biological feature - the delayed development of the embryo. After pollination, the ovule changes rather quickly, and by

the end of the first year it already has a thick membrane and a protein core filled with endosperm (nutritive tissue), but does not yet have a developed embryo. Outwardly, such an ovule looks like a seed, but due to the absence of a fully developed embryo, it is not suitable for germination, and is not a seed. In the matter of fruiting, the quality of the seeds is very important. As a result of numerous analyzes of seeds of all three forest-forming species of juniper growing in the Turskestan, Alai, Chatkal, Talas and Kirghiz ridges, an extremely high infestation by pests was established. The main reason for this situation is the clutter of juniper forests, as well as the lack of sanitary felling and other forest care measures. Infected trees are found at different heights at different exposures in stands of different densities.

However, there are certain patterns in the spread of pests of juniper seeds.

1. The highest infection of seeds of *J. seravschanica* and *J. turkestanica* is observed mainly in the middle part of the juniper belt, within the absolute heights of 2600-2800 m, i.e. where juniper forests are most concentrated.

2. The drier and warmer the slope occupied by plantations (regardless of the types of juniper), is the greater the degree of infestation is.

3. In all cases, pests affect the seeds of *J. semiglobosa*, then *J. turkestanica* and, to a lesser extent, *J. seravschanica*.

In addition to the high infestation by pests, the quality of seeds is also reduced due to a rather large number of empty seeds. The majority of empty seeds are usually in the *J. seravschanica* and less in the hemispherical. As a result of all this, the lowest seed quality (on average 30%) was noted in juniper *turkestanica*, then *J. seravschanica* (35%). In hemispherical juniper, the average percentage of good quality does not exceed 40%. Table 1 provides summary data on the quality of pine berries and seeds of forest-forming juniper species.

Table 1

The quality of the cone berries and seeds	Type of juniper					
	<i>J. turkestanica</i>		<i>J. semiglobosa</i>		<i>J. seravschanica</i>	
	From to	In the middle	From to	In the middle	From to	In the middle
Lumpyagodi						
Weight 1000 pieces. gram	416-1250	800	100-188	144	350-750	500
Pieces in 1 kg	800-2400	1200	3100-5700	4000	1500-2700	2000
Seeds						
% exit from pineapple	12-50	35	8-42	26	15-32	24
Weight 1000 pcs, g	120-166	154	15-30	21	42-67	54
Healthy seeds,%	10-60	30	10-80	40	10-60	35

The table shows that in order to obtain one kilogram of good seeds that are 100% suitable for sowing, with their best quality and high yield, it is necessary to prepare at least 3 kg of cones of each type of juniper. With poor quality and low yield, in order to obtain one kilogram of good seeds, it is necessary to prepare 70-80 kg of *J. turkestanica* and *J. seravschanica* cones, and 125 kg for *J. seravschanica*. At average rates, to obtain one kilogram of good-quality seeds, 10-12 kg of cones of each type of juniper will be required. Seedlings in plantations appear not earlier than June, when the air and soil are already warming up well, but still contain enough moisture. The seedlings of juniper of the *turkestanica* cotyledon and stem are fat, like no other species of juniper. Cotyledons are blue-green, convex above, depressed below, edges are slightly curved. The needles are dark green with a bluish tinge. Above with a convex middle, with two wide deepened stripes, painted in a deep blue-green color. The bottom plate is keeled, all monochrome, green.

The development of natural seedlings is very slow: the growth does not exceed 1 cm per year, and branching is observed only in the second year, and sometimes even later. The slow development of seedlings under natural conditions is due to the extremely short growing season, no more than 2-3 months per summer. The beginning of the growing season is delayed by a lack of heat, and the end is caused by the dryness of the soil, which has been observed in juniper forests since the end of August. In irrigated nurseries, with good care, juniper seedlings develop much faster: at the age of one, the average height of the *J. seravschanica* is 6-7 cm, that of hemispherical ones is 4-5cm, and at the age of two, respectively the height is 12-20cm and 8-10 cm accordingly.

Output. We follow the conclusion that if you prepare juniper cones for sowing to biological dormancy, you can get results by next spring. Reproduction of juniper by seeds in natural conditions is very difficult. For this purpose, the seeds need to be collected on time and to be planted in the nursery. Even after the growth, it can be clearly seen that the seedling grown in nurseries is better than that grown in natural conditions.

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